

FACTORS AFFECTING THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM

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Annotation: this scientific article mainly presents the factors that influence the development of the tourism industry. The tourism sector in world history has also been touched upon separately.

Keywords: Tourism, International roads, domestic tourism, food industry, urban welfare.

The development of international tourism is carried out by construction, a modern airport, roads, shops, cinemas, the well-being of cities, the installation of monuments, etc. In addition to the sectors closely related to tourism, the economy also has its influence on the automotive industry, food, textile industries, clothing, etc. The allocation of funds for the construction of the hotel will accelerate the rise of the industry. Foreign tourism has a significant impact on the food industry. Many tourists do not use the services of a hotel by forgiving relatives and acquaintances, renting houses or living in private villas. This category of foreign tourists spends a lot of money on the purchase of food. For example, at the expense of the French, the costs that foreign tourists spend on the purchase of food are 8.4% of the profit from all foreign tourism. Here it is necessary to take into account that the journey of the French in France itself does not bring such significant receipts, but the cost of foreign travelers will bring a lot of valuta to the country. Thus, tourists demand to expand the consumer market. In particular, as a result of the development of autotourism in France, kata led to the production of special semi-finished products in quantities. Speaking about autotourism, it should be noted that 14.6% of foreign tourism revenues fall on oil-and-oil products. The growth of tourism will give impetus to the expansion of road construction, which is one of the most important factors in the overall economic growth of the country. For the construction of 12 tourist centers with 101 thousand seats in France, 127 large roads were built. These factors indicate that tourism has always stimulated the conditions in the country. The development of Tourism ultimately leads to the development of Public production contributes to the growth of labor productivity, improvement of its systems, even in those areas of the economy that are not directly related to tourism. International tourist consumption stimulates multifaceted economic processes, opens up additional markets for non-profit sectors, thereby creating conditions for the development of production, the application of new technology. It is also confirmed that it has a significant impact on areas that are not directly related to tourism, such as the fact that 10 ministries in France allocate certain funds for the tourism industry. International tourist consumption, which has a characteristic power in all respects, leads to the expansion of many industries, and in this affects from the best brand to the production of mechanical lifts for skiing. Such a wide development of tourism has given rise to a new type of car that is a caravan (wheeled House-pritsep). In subsequent years, another amazing type of car was discovered — camping-karov (a self-propelled house with synthetic and kitchen equipment).

The emergence of tourist centers along the seas includes yachts, parusnik, kater, and the development of mountain tourism includes ski equipment requires reproduction.

Tourism contributes to general economic growth, the development of poorly developed regions. Opening tourist centers in poorly developed regions is the main method of many countries. The creation of a tourist center in Mountain and rural areas contributes to the assimilation of these places, an improvement in the living conditions of the population. The development of international and national tourism can bring new life to many rural areas, promote the population's cipsation and be a great incentive to organize the production of agricultural products in this place itself. A vivid example of this would be taking the village of Ossua, which was in a deplorable state in the 60s. In 100 years, half of the population of this Earth disappeared: in 1961, 766 people lived in it, and in 1962, 339 people remained. Many believe that this village was doomed to death. It is important to mention that the rural population was engaged in agriculture, in 1976 only 4 families remained in Hilda. The local government immediately decided on the development of Mountain Tourism. The construction of mechanical lifts and tourist bases was put on YOI. Between 1981 and 1983, 700-seat hotels were built, and later the intention was to raise this number to 3ming. Thus, the foundation was laid for the development of the local economy.

In subsequent years, it became customary in many countries for townspeople to have fun on farms. This led to the fact that the villagers have the opportunity to have a second specialty related to tourism, and to thoroughly get the living conditions with the construction and commissioning of a tourist complex in places. One of the characteristic aspects of the tourism industry is the service enterprise in the system of the international division of Labor. As a result of the development of foreign tourism, this service enterprise begins to sell its services as a product, like other goods. Specialization in service for international tourism leads to a drop in funds. The tourism industry affects the overall expansion of the scale of Service, an increase in the income of the population in the regions. With the expansion of the scale of international tourism, the number of service enterprises will also increase. The sphere of influence on tourism includes many types of coraonas, and they are launched during the tourist season, the turnover of which goes back depending on the number of tourists. The service sectors that affect international tourism include food, clothing, footwear, jewelry, antiques, perfume shops, attoral goods, flower shop, tobacco products store, construction and repair, laundry services, gas stations, etc.k. enters. The development of international tourism can lead to unprecedented economic growth in the region. An example of this is Lord, One of the 3 cities in Europe, which is a center of worship. This town with a population of 5 thousand people has its own tourist resources: a castle, a remnant of an ancient fortress turned into a prison on a mountain.

By 1858, a miracle happened in this city. The source found in the city was recognized as miraculous and thousands of people began to flock to the Lord. Entrepreneurs began to take advantage of this. While the year of the appearance of the miracle in the city was only 2 hotels, 100 years later the Lord became the city with the largest hotels in Europe. In the 80s, he ranked 2nd among French cities in terms of the number of hotels. 226 hotels in the city are served by 3,000 workers. Every year the city receives 3.5 million tourists, of which 59% are foreigners. Only in the same developed region of tourism is it very dangerous that demand drops sharply. A crisis in the economy of this region can also occur as a result of depreciation of the place of travel, lack of interest in people, a decrease in tourists. An example of this

would be taking mineral water resorts in France. France has 120 sources of mineral water. These are the richest sources in all of Europe, not only in number, but also in the number of minerals contained in water. On the eve of World War II, French mineral water Resorts took the first place in the world. Only in later times, the material and technical base created before the first World War was not renewed, since the owners of the resource spent their capital on pumping and packaging mineral waters. As a result, France received 2 billion a year. it has become a large complex for the production of liters of mineral water, while the traffic of foreign tourists has also decreased, which causes damage to the economy of the region, that is, a strain, in which tourism plays a key role.

To determine the future of the development of tourism, it is necessary to study in depth the awalo, the material and technical base, the scale of tourist resources, the demand for this tourist product. In this work, one should not overdo the assessment of tourist resources. For example, a historical monument in a particular region can be interesting only for the place itself, while in the international arena, in front of many other monuments, this monument may not be so important and attract tourists, and therefore, in such regions, it is imperative to make a lot of profit from the creation of a material and technical base mahol. When assessing the tourist resource, it will also be necessary to take into account the resources in the neighboring district. The demand that tourist fashion imposes (for example, going on a trip on horses, etc.)kjni should also not be overlooked.

Now studying scientific heritage, socio-political activities and acquaintance youth charity of our above-stated ancestors is considered one of the main urgent objectives of the modern intellectuals.

In this article are given the importance, role, types of the family in modern society. Its development from ancient times till present is widely described in this article.

Thus, The Tourist Center, which is represented in the backward region, leads to its development. In addition, the establishment of such "development poles" will lead to a deepening of economic dysproportion in the future. It is clear that if the tourist policy does not contradict the interests of the region, international tourism in itself cannot guarantee the prosperity of the local economy.

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